

$\pi g\eta$ -CLOSED SETS AND SOME RELATED TOPICS

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Abstract: In this paper, we introduce a new class of sets called $\pi g\eta$ -closed sets in topological spaces and investigate the relationship with other existing generalized closed sets. Moreover, we also introduce and studied the concepts of $\pi g\eta$ -continuous and $\pi g\eta$ -irresolute functions via $\pi g\eta$ -closed sets which are defined by me. We obtain some properties about $\pi g\eta$ -closed sets, $\pi g\eta$ -continuous and $\pi g\eta$ -irresolute functions, and $\pi g\eta$ -compactness.

2010 AMS Subject Classification: 54C08, 54C10, 54D10, 54D30.

Keywords: $\pi g\eta$ -closed, $\pi g\eta$ -continuity, $\pi g\eta$ -irresoluteness, $\pi g\eta$ -compactness.

1. Introduction

Many investigations related to generalized closed sets and generalized continuous functions have been published in various forms of closed sets and continuous functions. In 1937, Stone [15] introduced the notion of regular open sets. In 1965, Njastad [13] introduced the concept of α -open sets. In 1968, the notion of π -open sets were introduced by Zaitsev [18] which are weaker form of regular open sets in topological spaces. In 1969, Singal and Mathur [14] introduced and studied the concept of nearly compact spaces. In 1970, Levine [10] initiated the study of so called generalized closed (briefly g -closed) sets. In 1993, Maki et al. [12] introduced the concept of α - T_0 and α - T_0 spaces. In 1994, Maki et al. [11] introduced the notion of αg -closed sets. In 2000, Dontchev and Noiri [5] introduced the notion of πg -closed sets. In 2007, Arockiarani and Janaki [1] introduced the notion of $\pi g\alpha$ -closed sets in topological spaces. In 2009, Janaki [8] Studied $\pi g\alpha$ -closed sets in topology. In 2019, Subbulakshmi, Sumathi, Indirani [16] introduced and investigated the notion of η -open sets. Recently, Kumar and Sharma [9] introduced and investigated the notion of η - T_k ($k = 0, 1, 2$) and η - R_k ($k = 0, 1, 2$) axioms in topological spaces.

2. Preliminaries

Throughout this paper, spaces (X, \mathfrak{I}) , (Y, σ) , and (Z, γ) (or simply X , Y and Z) always mean topological spaces on which no separation axioms are assumed unless explicitly stated. Let A be a subset of a space X . The closure of A and interior of A are denoted by $Cl(A)$ and $Int(A)$ respectively. A subset A is said to be **regular open** [15] (resp. **regular closed** [15]) if $A = Int(Cl(A))$ (resp. $A = Cl(Int(A))$). The finite union of regular open sets is said to be **π -open** [18]. The complement of a π -open set is said to be **π -closed** [18].

Definition 2.1. A subset A of a topological space (X, \mathfrak{I}) is said to be

- (i) **α -open** [13] if $A \subset Int(Cl(Int(A)))$.
- (ii) **η -open** [16] if $A \subset In(Cl(Int(A))) \cup Cl(Int(A))$.
- (iii) **η -closed** [16] if $A \supset Cl(Int(Cl(A))) \cup Int(Cl(A))$.

The complement of a **α -open** set is called **α -closed**. The intersection of all α -closed (resp. η -closed) sets containing A , is called **α -closure** (resp. **η -closure**) of A , and is denoted by **α -Cl(A)** (resp. **η -Cl(A)**). The **η -interior** of A , denoted by **η -Int(A)** is defined as union of all η -open sets contained in A . We denote the family of all η -open (resp. η -closed) sets of a topological space by **η -O(X)** (resp. **η -C(X)**).

Definition 2.2. A subset A of a space (X, \mathfrak{I}) is said to be

- (1) **generalized closed** (briefly **g -closed**) [10] if $Cl(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and $U \in \mathfrak{I}$.
- (2) **πg -closed** [5] if $Cl(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is π -open in X .
- (3) **α -generalized closed** (briefly **αg -closed**) [11] if α -Cl(A) $\subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and $U \in \mathfrak{I}$.

- (4) **$\pi g\alpha$ -closed** [1] if $\alpha\text{-Cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is π -open in X .
 (5) **generalized η -closed** (briefly **$g\eta$ -closed**) [17] if $\eta\text{-Cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and $U \in \mathfrak{S}$.
 (6) **g -open** (resp. **πg -open, αg -open, $\pi g\alpha$ -open, $g\eta$ -open**) set if the complement of A is g -closed (resp. πg -closed, αg -closed, $\pi g\alpha$ -closed, $g\eta$ -closed).

Lemma 2.3. For any subsets A and B of a space (X, \mathfrak{S}) the following hold:

- (a) $\eta\text{-Cl}(A) = A \cup [\text{Cl}(\text{Int}(\text{Cl}(A))) \cap \text{Int}(\text{Cl}(A))]$,
 (b) $\eta\text{-Cl}(X - A) = X - \eta\text{-Int}(A)$,
 (c) $x \in \eta\text{-Cl}(A)$ if and only if $A \cap U \neq \emptyset$ for every $U \in \eta\text{-O}(X, x)$,
 (d) $A \in \eta\text{-C}(X)$ if and only if $A = \eta\text{-Cl}(A)$.

3. $\pi g\eta$ -closed Sets

Definition 3.1. A subset A of a space (X, \mathfrak{S}) is said to be **$\pi g\eta$ -closed** if $\eta\text{-Cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is π -open in X . The family of all $\pi g\eta$ -closed subsets of X will be denoted by $\pi g\eta\text{-C}(X)$.

Theorem 3.2. Every closed set is $\pi g\eta$ -closed.

Proof. Let A be a closed set in X . Let U be a π -open set in X such that $A \subset U$. Since A is closed, that is, $\text{Cl}(A) = A$, $\text{Cl}(A) \subset U$. But we have $\eta\text{-Cl}(A) \subset \text{Cl}(A) \subset U$. Therefore $\eta\text{-Cl}(A) \subset U$. Hence A is $\pi g\eta$ -closed in X .

Theorem 3.3. For a topological space X the followings hold:

- (1) Every g -closed set is $\pi g\eta$ -closed.
 (2) Every πg -closed set is $\pi g\eta$ -closed.
 (3) Every α -closed set is $\pi g\eta$ -closed.
 (4) Every αg -closed set is $\pi g\eta$ -closed.
 (5) Every $\pi g\alpha$ -closed set is $\pi g\eta$ -closed.

Proof.

(1) Let A be a g -closed set in X . Let U be a π -open set in X such that $A \subset U$. Since every π -open set is open and since A is g -closed, that is, $\text{Cl}(A) \subset U$. But we have $\eta\text{-Cl}(A) \subset \text{Cl}(A) \subset U$. Therefore $\eta\text{-Cl}(A) \subset U$. Hence A is $\pi g\eta$ -closed in X .

(2) Let A be a πg -closed set in X . Let U be a π -open set in X such that $A \subset U$. Since A is πg -closed, that is, $\text{Cl}(A) \subset U$. But we have $\eta\text{-Cl}(A) \subset \text{Cl}(A) \subset U$. Therefore $\eta\text{-Cl}(A) \subset U$. Hence A is $\pi g\eta$ -closed in X .

(3) Let A be a α -closed set in X . Let U be a π -open set in X such that $A \subset U$. Since A is α -closed, that is, $\alpha\text{-Cl}(A) = A$, $\alpha\text{-Cl}(A) \subset U$. But we have $\eta\text{-Cl}(A) \subset \alpha\text{-Cl}(A) \subset U$. Therefore $\eta\text{-Cl}(A) \subset U$. Hence A is $\pi g\eta$ -closed in X .

(4) Let A be a αg -closed set in X . Let U be a π -open set in X such that $A \subset U$. Since every π -open set is open and since A is αg -closed, that is, $\alpha\text{-Cl}(A) \subset U$. But we have $\eta\text{-Cl}(A) \subset \alpha\text{-Cl}(A) \subset U$. Therefore $\eta\text{-Cl}(A) \subset U$. Hence A is $\pi g\eta$ -closed in X .

(5) Let A be a $\pi g\alpha$ -closed set in X . Let U be a π -open set in X such that $A \subset U$. Since A is $\pi g\alpha$ -closed, that is, $\alpha\text{-Cl}(A) \subset U$. But we have $\eta\text{-Cl}(A) \subset \alpha\text{-Cl}(A) \subset U$. Therefore $\eta\text{-Cl}(A) \subset U$. Hence A is $\pi g\eta$ -closed in X .

Remark 3.4. From the above definitions, theorems and known results the relationship between $\pi g\eta$ -closed sets and some other existing generalized closed sets are implemented in the following Figure:

Where none of the implications is reversible as can be seen from the following examples:

Example 3.5. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, X\}$. Then $A = \{a, b, c\}$ and $B = \{a, b, d\}$ are πg -closed as well as $\pi g \eta$ -closed but not closed.

Example 3.6. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{d\}, \{a, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, X\}$. Then $A = \{c\}$ is $\pi g \alpha$ -closed as well as $\pi g \eta$ -closed. But it is neither closed nor g -closed. It is not πg -closed.

Example 3.7. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}, X\}$. Then $A = \{b\}$ is g -closed, αg -closed, $g \eta$ -closed, $\pi g \alpha$ -closed, $\pi g \eta$ -closed. But it is closed.

Example 3.8. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{c\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, X\}$. Then $A = \{a, b\}$ is $\pi g \alpha$ -closed as well as $\pi g \eta$ -closed but not closed. But it is neither closed nor αg -closed.

Example 3.9. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, X\}$. Then $A = \{c\}$ is η -closed as well as $\pi g \eta$ -closed but not α -closed.

Example 3.10. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b, c\}, X\}$. Then $A = \{a, b\}$ is $g \eta$ -closed as well as $\pi g \eta$ -closed but not closed.

Theorem 3.11. For $\pi g \eta$ -closed sets of a space (X, \mathfrak{T}) the following properties hold:

- Every finite union of $\pi g \eta$ -closed sets is always a $\pi g \eta$ -closed set.
- Even a countable union of $\pi g \eta$ -closed sets need not be a $\pi g \eta$ -closed set.
- Even a finite intersection of $\pi g \eta$ -closed sets may fail to be a $\pi g \eta$ -closed set.

Proof.

(a) Let A and B be any two $\pi g \eta$ -closed sets. Therefore $\eta\text{-Cl}(A) \subset U$ and $\eta\text{-Cl}(B) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$, $B \subset U$ and U is π -open. Let $A \cup B \subset U$ where U is π -open.

Since, $\eta\text{-Cl}(A \cup B) \subset \eta\text{-Cl}(A) \cup \eta\text{-Cl}(B) \subset U$, we have $A \cup B$ is $\pi g \eta$ -closed.

(b) Let R be the real line with the usual topology. Every singleton is $\pi g \eta$ -closed. However, $A = \{1/i : i = 2, 3, \dots\}$ is not $\pi g \eta$ -closed, since $A \subset (0, 1)$ which is π -open but $\eta\text{-Cl}(A) \not\subset (0, 1)$.

(c) Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and let $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, X\}$. Let $A = \{a, b, c\}$ and $B = \{a, b, d\}$ are $\pi g \eta$ -closed sets. But $A \cap B = \{a, b\} \subset \{a, b\}$ which is π -open. $\eta\text{-Cl}(A \cap B) \not\subset \{a, b\}$. Hence $A \cap B$ is not $\pi g \eta$ -closed.

Theorem 3.12: If A is $\pi g \eta$ -closed and B is any set $A \subset B \subset \eta\text{-Cl}(A)$ then B is $\pi g \eta$ -closed.

Proof: Since A is $\pi g \eta$ -closed, $\eta\text{-Cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is π -open. Let $B \subset U$ and U is π -open. Since $B \subset \eta\text{-Cl}(A)$, $\eta\text{-Cl}(B) \subset \eta\text{-Cl}(A) \subset U$. Hence B is $\pi g \eta$ -closed.

Theorem 3.13. Let A be a $\pi g \eta$ -closed set in X . Then $\eta\text{-Cl}(A) - A$ does not contain any nonempty π -closed set.

Proof. Let F be a nonempty π -closed set such that $F \subset \eta\text{-Cl}(A) - A$. Then $F \subset \eta\text{-Cl}(A) \cap (X - A) \subset (X - A)$ implies $A \subset X - F$ where $X - F$ is π -open. Therefore $\eta\text{-Cl}(A) \subset X - F$ implies $F \subset (\eta\text{-Cl}(A))^c$. Now $F \subset \eta\text{-Cl}(A) \cap (\eta\text{-Cl}(A))^c$ implies F is empty.

Reverse implication does not hold.

Example 3.14. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d, e\}$ and let $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, \{a, b\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, c, d\}, X\}$. Let $A = \{c\}$ then $\eta\text{-Cl}(A) = \{c, d, e\}$, $\eta\text{-Cl}(A) - A = \{d, e\}$ does not contain any nonempty regular closed set but A is not $\pi g \eta$ -closed set.

Corollary 3.15. Let A be $\pi g \eta$ -closed. A is η -closed iff $\eta\text{-Cl}(A) - A$ is π -closed.

Proof. Let A be η -closed set then $A = \eta\text{-Cl}(A)$ implies $\eta\text{-Cl}(A) - A = \phi$ which is π -closed. Conversely, if $\eta\text{-Cl}(A) - A$ is π -closed then A is η -closed.

Theorem 3.16. If A is π -open and $\pi g\eta$ -closed. Then A is η -closed and hence clopen.

Proof. Let A be regular open. Since A is $\pi g\eta$ -closed, $\eta\text{-Cl}(A) \subset A$ implies A is η -closed. Hence A is closed. (Since every π -open η -closed set is closed). Therefore A is clopen.

Definition 3.17. Let (X, \mathfrak{T}) be a topological space, $A \subset X$ and $x \in X$. Then x is said to be a **η -limit point** of A iff every η -open set containing x contains a point of A different from x , and the set of all η -limit points of A is said to be the η -derived set of A and is denoted by $D_\eta(A)$.

Usual derived set of A is denoted by $D(A)$.

The proof of the following result is analogous to the well known ones.

Lemma 3.18. Let (X, \mathfrak{T}) be a topological space and $A \subset X$. Then $\eta\text{-Cl}(A) = A \cup D_\eta(A)$.

Theorem 3.19. Let A and B be $\pi g\eta$ -closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) such that $\text{Cl}(A) = \eta\text{-Cl}(A)$ and $\text{Cl}(B) = \eta\text{-Cl}(B)$. Then $A \cup B$ is $\pi g\eta$ -closed.

Proof. Let $A \cup B \subset U$ and U is π -open in (X, \mathfrak{T}) . Then $\eta\text{-Cl}(A) \subset U$ and $\eta\text{-Cl}(B) \subset U$. Now, $\text{Cl}(A \cup B) = \text{Cl}(A) \cup \text{Cl}(B) = \eta\text{-Cl}(A) \cup \eta\text{-Cl}(B) \subset U$. But $\eta\text{-Cl}(A \cup B) \subset \text{Cl}(A \cup B)$. So, $\eta\text{-Cl}(A \cup B) \subset U$ and hence $A \cup B$ is $\pi g\eta$ -closed.

From the fact that $D_\eta(A) \subset D(A)$ and **Lemma 3.18** we have the following,

Remark 3.20. For any subset $A \subset X$ such that $D(A) \subset D_\eta(A)$. Then $\text{Cl}(A) = \eta\text{-Cl}(A)$.

Theorem 3.21. For a space X , the following are equivalent:

- (a) X is extremally disconnected,
- (b) Every subset of X is $\pi g\eta$ -closed,
- (c) The topology on X generated by $\pi g\eta$ -closed sets is the discrete ones.

Proof. (a) \Rightarrow (b).

Assume that X is extremally disconnected. Let $A \subset U$ where U is π -open in X . Since U is π -open, it is the finite union of regular open sets and X is extremally disconnected, U is finite union of clopen sets and hence U is clopen. Therefore $\eta\text{-cl}(A) \subset \text{cl}(A) \subset \text{cl}(U) \subset U$ implies A is $\pi g\eta$ -closed.

(b) \Rightarrow (a).

Let A be a regular open set of X . Since A is $\pi g\eta$ -closed by **Theorem 3.16**, A is clopen. Hence X is extremally disconnected.

(b) \Leftrightarrow (c) is obvious.

4. $\pi g\eta$ -open sets

Definition 4.1. Let (X, \mathfrak{T}) be a topological space. A subset A of X is called **π -generalized η -open** (briefly **$\pi g\eta$ -open**) iff its complement is $\pi g\eta$ -closed set. We denote the family of all $\pi g\eta$ -open (resp. $\pi g\eta$ -closed) sets of a topological space by **$\pi g\eta\text{-O}(X)$** (resp. **$\pi g\eta\text{-C}(X)$**).

Lemma 4.2. If A be a subset of X , then

- (a) $\eta\text{-Cl}(X - A) = X - \eta\text{-Int}(A)$.
- (b) $\eta\text{-Int}(X - A) = X - \eta\text{-Cl}(A)$.

Theorem 4.3. A subset A of a space X is $\pi g\eta$ -open iff $F \subset \eta\text{-Int}(A)$ whenever F is π -closed and $F \subset A$.

Proof. Let F be π -closed set such that $F \subset A$. Since $X - A$ is $\pi g\eta$ -closed and $X - A \subset X - F$ where $F \subset \eta\text{-Int}(A)$. Conversely,

Let $F \subset \eta\text{-Int}(A)$ where F is π -closed and $F \subset A$. Since $F \subset A$ and $X - F$ is π -open, $\eta\text{-Cl}(X - A) = X - \eta\text{-Int}(A) \subset X - F$. Therefore A is $\pi\eta$ -open.

Theorem 4.4. If $\eta\text{-Int}(A) \subset B \subset A$ and A $\pi\eta$ -open then B is $\pi\eta$ -open.

Proof: Since $\eta\text{-Int}(A) \subset B \subset A$, by **Theorem 3.12**, $\eta\text{-Cl}(X - A) \supset (X - B)$ implies B is $\pi\eta$ -open.

Remark 4.5. For any $A \subset X$, $\eta\text{-Int}(\eta\text{-Cl}(A) - A) = \phi$.

Theorem 4.6. If $A \subset X$ is $\pi\eta$ -closed then $\eta\text{-Cl}(A) - A$ is $\pi\eta$ -open.

Proof. Let A be $\pi\eta$ -closed and F be a π -closed set such that $F \subset \eta\text{-Cl}(A) - A$. By **Theorem 3.13**, $F = \emptyset$ implies $F \subset \eta\text{-Int}(\eta\text{-Cl}(A) - A)$. By **Theorem 4.3**, $\eta\text{-cl}(A) - A$ is $\pi\eta$ -open.

Converse of the above theorem is not true.

Example 4.7. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and let $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, X\}$. Let $A = \{b\}$. Then A is not $\pi\eta$ -closed but $\eta\text{-Cl}(A) - A = \{a, b\}$ is $\pi\eta$ -open.

Definition 4.8. A topological space X is called a **$\pi\eta\text{-}T_{1/2}$ space** if every $\pi\eta$ -closed set is η -closed.

Theorem 4.9. Let (X, \mathfrak{T}) be a topological space.

(a) $\eta\text{-O}(X) \subset \pi\eta\text{-O}(X)$,

(b) A space X is $\pi\eta\text{-}T_{1/2}$ iff $\eta\text{-O}(X) = \pi\eta\text{-O}(X)$.

Proof. (a) Let A be a η -open set, then $X - A$ is η -closed so $X - A$ is $\pi\eta$ -closed. Thus A is $\pi\eta$ -open. Hence $\eta\text{-O}(X) \subset \pi\eta\text{-O}(X)$.

(b) Necessity: Let (X, \mathfrak{T}) be $\pi\eta\text{-}T_{1/2}$ space. Let A be $\pi\eta$ -open. Then $X - A$ is $\pi\eta$ -closed. By hypothesis, $X - A$ is η -closed. Thus A is η -open. Therefore $\eta\text{-O}(X) = \pi\eta\text{-O}(X)$.

Sufficiency: Let $\eta\text{-O}(X) = \pi\eta\text{-O}(X)$. Let A be $\pi\eta$ -closed. Then $X - A$ is $\pi\eta$ -open. $X - A$ is η -open. Hence A is η -closed. This implies (X, \mathfrak{T}) is $\pi\eta\text{-}T_{1/2}$ space.

Lemma 4.10. Let A be a subset of X and $x \in X$. Then $x \in \eta\text{-Cl}(A)$ iff $V \cap \{x\} \neq \phi$ for every η -open set V containing x .

Theorem 4.11. For a topological space X the following are equivalent:

(a) X is $\pi\eta\text{-}T_{1/2}$ space.

(b) Every singleton set is either π -closed or η -open.

Proof. (a) \Rightarrow (b): Let X be a $\pi\eta\text{-}T_{1/2}$ space. Let $x \in X$ and assuming that $\{x\}$ is not π -closed. Then clearly $X - \{x\}$ is not π -open. Hence $X - \{x\}$ is trivially a $\pi\eta$ -closed. Since X is $\pi\eta\text{-}T_{1/2}$ space, $X - \{x\}$ is η -closed. Therefore $\{x\}$ is η -open.

(b) \Rightarrow (a): Assume every singleton set of X is either π -closed or η -open. Let A be a $\pi\eta$ -closed set. Let $x \in \eta\text{-Cl}(A)$.

Case I: Let $\{x\}$ be π -closed. Suppose x does not belong to A . Then $x \in \eta\text{-Cl}(A) - A$. By **Theorem 3.7**, $x \in A$. Hence $\eta\text{-Cl}(A) \subset A$.

Case II: Let $\{x\}$ be η -open. Since $x \in \eta\text{-Cl}(A)$, we have $A \cap \{x\} \neq \phi$ implies $x \in A$. Therefore $\eta\text{-Cl}(A) \subset A$. Therefore A is η -closed.

5. $\pi\eta$ -continuous and $\pi\eta$ -irresolute Functions

Definition 5.1. A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is called:

(a) **α -continuous** [12] (resp. **η -continuous** [17]) if $f^{-1}(V)$ is α -closed (resp. η -closed) in X for every closed set V of Y ,

(b) **g -continuous** [3] (resp. **αg -continuous** [11], **$g\eta$ -continuous** [17]) if $f^{-1}(V)$ is g -closed (resp. αg -closed, $g\eta$ -closed) in X for every closed set V of Y ,

(c) πg -continuous [5] (resp. $\pi g\alpha$ -continuous [1], $\pi g\eta$ -continuous) if $f^{-1}(V)$ is πg -closed (resp. $\pi g\alpha$ -closed, $\pi g\eta$ -closed) in X for every closed set V of Y ,

Definition 5.2. A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is called η -irresolute [9] (resp. $g\eta$ -irresolute [17], $\pi g\eta$ -irresolute) if $f^{-1}(V)$ is η -closed (resp. $g\eta$ -closed, $\pi g\eta$ -closed) in X for every η -closed (resp. $g\eta$ -closed, $\pi g\eta$ -closed) set V of Y .

Proposition 5.3. Every $\pi g\eta$ -irresolute function is $\pi g\eta$ -continuous.

Remark 5.4. From the above definitions, proposition and known results, we have following diagram:

Where none of the implications is reversible as can be seen from the following examples:

Example 5.5. Let $X = \{x, y, z\}$, $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, X, \{x\}\}$, $Y = \{a, b\}$ and $\rho = \{\phi, Y, \{a\}\}$. Define $f : (X, \mathfrak{T}) \rightarrow (Y, \rho)$ as follows: $f(x) = f(z) = b$ and $f(y) = a$. Then f is g -continuous as well as $g\eta$ -continuous. It is also $\pi g\eta$ -continuous but not continuous.

Example 5.6. Let $X = \{x, y, z\}$, $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, X, \{x\}, \{y\}, \{x, y\}\}$ and $f : (X, \mathfrak{T}) \rightarrow (X, \mathfrak{T})$ defined as follows: $f(x) = f(y) = x$ and $f(z) = z$. Then f is π -continuous as well as continuous.

Example 5.7. Let $X = Y = \{x, y, z\}$, $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, X, \{x\}, \{z\}, \{x, z\}\}$ and $\rho = \{\phi, Y, \{x\}, \{y\}, \{x, y\}\}$. Define $f : (X, \mathfrak{T}) \rightarrow (Y, \rho)$ as follows: $f(x) = x$, $f(y) = z$ and $f(z) = y$. Then $f^{-1}(\{z\}) = \{y\}$, $f^{-1}(\{x, z\}) = \{x, y\}$, $f^{-1}(\{y, z\}) = \{y, z\}$. Therefore, f is $g\eta$ -continuous as well as $\pi g\eta$ -continuous.

Example 5.8. Let $X = Y = \{x, y, z\}$, $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, X, \{x\}, \{y, z\}\}$ and $\rho = \{\phi, Y, \{x\}, \{z\}, \{x, z\}\}$. Define $f : (X, \mathfrak{T}) \rightarrow (Y, \rho)$ as follows: $f(x) = z$, $f(y) = y$ and $f(z) = x$. Then $f^{-1}(\{y\}) = \{y\}$ is not closed, α -closed in X . Here the set $\{y\}$ is closed in Y . Therefore, f is not continuous, α -continuous.

Example 5.9. Let $X = Y = \{x, y, z\}$, $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, X, \{x\}, \{z\}, \{x, z\}\}$ and $\rho = \{\phi, Y, \{y, z\}\}$. Define $f : (X, \mathfrak{T}) \rightarrow (Y, \rho)$ as follows: $f(x) = x$, $f(y) = z$ and $f(z) = y$. Then f is $g\eta$ -continuous as well as $\pi g\eta$ -continuous.

Example 5.10. Let $X = Y = \{x, y, z\}$, $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, X, \{y, z\}\}$ and $\rho = \{\phi, Y, \{x\}\}$. Define $f : (X, \mathfrak{T}) \rightarrow (Y, \rho)$ as follows: $f(x) = y$, $f(y) = z$ and $f(z) = x$. Then f is $g\eta$ -continuous as well as $\pi g\eta$ -continuous.

Example 5.11. Let $X = Y = \{x, y, z\}$, $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, X, \{x\}, \{z\}, \{x, z\}\}$ and $\rho = \{\phi, Y, \{x\}, \{y\}, \{x, y\}\}$. Define $f : (X, \mathfrak{T}) \rightarrow (Y, \rho)$ as follows: $f(x) = x$, $f(y) = z$ and $f(z) = y$. Then $f^{-1}(\{x\}) = \{x\}$, $f^{-1}(\{y\}) = \{z\}$, $f^{-1}(\{z\}) = \{y\}$, $f^{-1}(\{x, z\}) = \{x, y\}$, $f^{-1}(\{y, z\}) = \{y, z\}$. Since inverse image of every $g\eta$ -open set in Y is $g\eta$ -open in X . Therefore, f is $g\eta$ -irresolute as well as $g\eta$ -continuous. It is also $\pi g\eta$ -continuous.

Theorem 5.12. Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be a function.

(a) If f is $\pi g\eta$ -irresolute and X is $\pi g\eta$ - $T_{1/2}$ space, then f is η -irresolute.

(b) If f is $\pi g\eta$ -continuous and X is $\pi g\eta$ - $T_{1/2}$ space, then f is η -continuous.

Proof. (a) Let V be η -closed in Y . Since f is $\pi g\eta$ -irresolute, $f^{-1}(V)$ is $\pi g\eta$ -closed in X . Since X is $\pi g\eta$ - $T_{1/2}$ space, $f^{-1}(V)$ is η -closed in X . Hence f is η -irresolute.

(b) Let V be closed in Y . Since f is $\pi g\eta$ -continuous, $f^{-1}(V)$ is $\pi g\eta$ -closed in X . By assumption, it is η -

closed. Therefore f is η -continuous.

Definition 5.13. A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is called **π -irresolute** [2] if $f^{-1}(V)$ is π -closed in X for each π -closed set V of Y .

Definition 5.14. A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is called **pre η -closed** if $f(V)$ is η -closed in Y for each η -closed set V of X .

Theorem 5.15. Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be π -irresolute and pre η -closed map. Then $f(A)$ is $\pi\eta$ -closed in Y for every $\pi\eta$ -closed set A of X .

Proof. Let A be $\pi\eta$ -closed set in X . Let $f(A) \subset V$ where V is π -open in Y . Then $A \subset f^{-1}(V)$ and A is $\pi\eta$ -closed in X implies $\eta\text{-Cl}(A) \subset f^{-1}(V)$. Hence $\eta\text{-Cl}(f(A)) \subset \eta\text{-Cl}(f(\eta\text{-Cl}(A))) = f(\eta\text{-Cl}(A)) \subset V$. Therefore $f(A)$ is $\pi\eta$ -closed in Y .

Definition 5.16. A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is **π -open map** [8] if $f(V)$ is π -open set in Y for every π -open set V of X .

Theorem 5.17. If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is η -irresolute and π -open bijection, then f is $\pi\eta$ -irresolute.

Proof. Let V be $\pi\eta$ -closed set in Y . Let $f^{-1}(V) \subset U$ where U is π -open in X . Hence $V \subset f(U)$ and $f(U)$ is π -open implies $\eta\text{-Cl}(V) \subset f(U)$. Since f is η -irresolute, $f^{-1}(\eta\text{-Cl}(V))$ is η -closed in X . Hence $\eta\text{-Cl}(f^{-1}(V)) \subset \eta\text{-Cl}(f^{-1}(\eta\text{-Cl}(V))) = f^{-1}(\eta\text{-Cl}(V)) \subset U$. Therefore $f^{-1}(V)$ is $\pi\eta$ -closed and thus f is $\pi\eta$ -irresolute.

Theorem 5.18. Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be pre η -closed and $\pi\eta$ -irresolute surjection. If X is $\pi\eta\text{-}T_{1/2}$ space, then Y is also a $\pi\eta\text{-}T_{1/2}$ space.

Proof. Let F be $\pi\eta$ -closed set in Y . Since f is $\pi\eta$ -irresolute, $f^{-1}(F)$ is $\pi\eta$ -closed in X . Since X is $\pi\eta\text{-}T_{1/2}$ space, $f^{-1}(F)$ is η -closed in X and hence $f(f^{-1}(F)) = F$ is η -closed in Y . This shows that Y is $\pi\eta\text{-}T_{1/2}$ space.

6. Some Covering Properties

Definition 6.1. A topological space X is said to be:

- nearly compact** [14] if every regular open cover of X has a finite subcover.
- countably compact** [4] if every open countable cover of X has a finite subcover.
- nearly countably compact** [7] if every countable cover by regular open sets has a finite subcover.
- nearly Lindelof** [6] if every cover by regular open sets has a countable subcover.
- $\pi\eta$ -compact** if every $\pi\eta$ -open cover of X has a finite subcover.
- $\pi\eta$ -Lindelof** if every cover by $\pi\eta$ -open sets has a countable subcover.
- countably $\pi\eta$ -compact** if every $\pi\eta$ -open countable cover of X has a finite subcover.

Corollary 6.2. For a topological space X the followings hold:

- If X is $\pi\eta$ -Lindelof, then X is Lindelof.
- If X is $\pi\eta$ -compact, then X is compact.
- If X is countably $\pi\eta$ -compact, then X is countably compact.
- If X is $\pi\eta$ -compact, then X is $\pi\eta$ -Lindelof.
- If X is $\pi\eta$ -compact, then X is nearly compact.
- If X is $\pi\eta$ -compact, then X is nearly Lindelof.
- If X is countably $\pi\eta$ -compact, then X is nearly countably compact.

Definition 6.3. A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is called **$\pi\eta$ -open** if $f(U)$ is $\pi\eta$ -closed in Y for each $\pi\eta$ -closed set in X .

Definition 6.4. A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is called **almost $\pi\eta$ -continuous** if $f^{-1}(V)$ is $\pi\eta$ -closed in X for every regular closed set V of Y .

Theorem 6.5. Every $\pi\eta$ -compact subset of a $\pi\eta$ -compact space is $\pi\eta$ -compact space relative to X .

Proof. Straightforward.

Theorem 6.6. Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be a function. If f is $\pi\eta$ -continuous surjection (resp. almost $\pi\eta$ -continuous) and X is $\pi\eta$ -compact space, then Y is compact (resp. nearly compact).

Proof. Straightforward.

Theorem 6.7. Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be a function and $A \subset X$. If f is $\pi\eta$ -irresolute and A is $\pi\eta$ -compact, then $f(A)$ is $\pi\eta$ -compact.

Proof. Straightforward.

Theorem 6.8. Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be a function. If f is $\pi\eta$ -open bijection and Y is $\pi\eta$ -compact, then X is $\pi\eta$ -compact.

Proof. Straightforward.

Remark 6.9. Every $\pi\eta$ -continuous function is almost $\pi\eta$ -continuous function.

Theorem 6.10. Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be an almost $\pi\eta$ -continuous surjection.

(a) If X is $\pi\eta$ -compact, then Y is nearly compact.

(b) If X is $\pi\eta$ -Lindelof, then Y is nearly Lindelof.

(c) If X is countably $\pi\eta$ -compact, then Y is nearly countably compact.

Proof. Straightforward.

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